

Melianthus comosus Kruidjie-roer-my-nie

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© D. Hoare

Group: Eudicot

Size: 1 meter in height

Distribution:

Melianthus comosus occurs mainly in the dry interior of South Africa, extending across seven of the nine South African provinces: North-West, Gauteng, Mpumalanga, Free State, Northern Cape, Western Cape and Eastern Cape. It also occurs in Namibia and Lesotho.

Importance:

The brightly coloured red flowers produce an abundance of black nectar that attracts sunbirds, Cape white eyes, bees and butterflies. Leaf and stem extractions are used to treat septic wounds, sores, bruises, backache and rheumatic joints. It is a traditional remedy for snakebite.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 39.21 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.91 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.88 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.7% [Single: 88.9%, Duplicated: 10.8%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 15 688.62 kilobases

Contig number: 13 435

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Date Published: 2025-10-29

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17378391>

